

RESPOND

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Global Migration: Consequences and Responses

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Conflicting conceptualizations of the future course of the European Union

Comparative Report

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About the project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project, which aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND studies migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanisation. Each thematic field between (1) and (5) is reflecting a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts and responses given by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). The present report is concerned with the comparative findings related to WP6.

Executive Summary

This comparative report draws together the research outputs of seven partners from the EU Horizon 2020 project RESPOND. Researchers in Hungary, Sweden, Austria, Germany, Greece, Poland and Italy had undertaken analysis of how contestation of migration was impacting on discursive constructions of “Europe” in mainstream politics and media. Drawing on post-functionalist theories of European order, we aimed to capture the growing politicisation and contestation of areas of EU governance that had previously been depoliticised in national politics. This analysis is then extended to examine the impact of contestation on European self-understanding at the supranational level.

Empirically, comparative analysis demonstrates the unevenness of how the politicisation of migration impacted on European politics. Participating countries were therefore grouped into three blocs. In Northern Europe (Austria, Germany and Sweden), humanitarian and liberal commitments formed a crucial component of early responses in discourse and policy. There was often significant initial support for burden-sharing and discourses of European solidarity, which in part reflected particular constructions of national history. However, such commitments waned under pressure from populist right-wing electoral competitors. These cases illustrate how fringe parties, without actively contending for government, may influence and shape the discourses of centrist governments.

The Southern European (Greece and Italy) were shaped by two influences: the extraordinary impact of austerity measures on political order, causing alternations between technocratic and populist rule; and the impact of geography on their experience of migration management. Both therefore experienced disproportionate impacts of the two major crises afflicting European politics. Unsurprisingly, then, anti-EU discourses were prevalent throughout mainstream politics and government. Main themes included being over-burdened by the Dublin Regulation and of the hypocrisy of Northern European states. However, such discourses were paradoxically balanced by underlying themes of “solidarity”: critiques of the EU were designed to achieve more support for relocation mechanisms. Furthermore, leftist and internationalist traditions continued to make impacts on present a broader concept of international solidarity, as with the Syriza government.

Eastern Europe (Hungary and Poland) presented an entirely different challenge. At the level of government, these countries were defined by pronounced dissidence to existing notions of Europeanisation, solidarity and humanitarianism. There was a pronounced focus on national sovereignty and themes of culture clash with Islamic populations. Equally, there was a broader Euro-populist appeal to “solidarity” with the European public against EU elites. Nonetheless, this illustrates the underlying “Euro-pragmatism” of governments seeking to influence and shape the European project according to their own values.

Finally, the report charts how “populist” narratives are impacting on supranational governance. Examining recent discourses of the European Commission, it shows how ideas previously associated with Eurosceptic dissidence have been embedded in the most seemingly cosmopolitan structures of the European project. This is exemplified by the contradictions in the “European way of life” agenda. Themes of incentivised “flexible solidarity” and externalisation of migration management reflect this broader shift. It demonstrates the inconsistencies and vulnerabilities of the European project in reconciling humanitarianism, democracy and national sovereignty.

1. Introduction

This comparative report draws on the RESPOND country reports from Hungary, Sweden, Austria, Germany, Greece, Poland and Italy to provide an overview of the dominant political claims and narratives by key political actors in the context of the so-called refugee crisis between 2014 and 2018. Furthermore, it considers how related political assumptions are reflected in the EU Commission's latest policy agenda.

The aim of this report is twofold. In the first part of this comparative study, we will account for political claims and narratives of national governmental actors in relation to the EU and external migration. Under the Horizon 2020 project RESPOND, we conducted a qualitative analysis of political discourses in seven EU member states involving various political parties both in government and in opposition. We studied how the aforementioned actors discursively construct the EU and its member states; narrate how external migration should be managed; and deliberate how migrants should be received and protected. More specifically, we selected public speeches that covered these topics and examined the way in which i) politicians publicly refer to the EU's institutional architecture as well as inter-state relationships; ii) how they evaluate existing European and national policies and proposed new ones; and iii) how they referred to immigrants and the domestic public as the primary audience of their speeches.

In section 4, we will discuss these claims along with three major narratives: national sovereignty vs. supranationalism, border control vs. humanitarianism, externalisation vs. burden sharing, and the economic value of migration. We clustered the cases in three groups: in the context of asylum, the central-northern group consisting of Austria, Germany and Sweden has been a major destination-block in recent years; the eastern group consisting of Hungary and Poland was adamant in their opposition to the admission of refugees; and the southern group represented by Italy and Greece was most strongly affected by the sudden increase in the number of refugee due to its geographical location. Examining these three groups and following their political narratives, we propose a comparative interpretation of evolving positions on external migration and the future course of Europeanization.

In the second part of this study, we examine how the diversity of claims and narratives within EU Member States is echoed in the EU Commission's "Migration and Asylum Package" introduced in September 2020 as well as the "European Way of Life" agenda that underpinned Ursula von der Leyen's Commission set up in 2019. We consider these two policy documents in view of how external migration was politicised in seven EU countries and the national priorities that emerged. On this basis, we examine them as attempts to reconcile the conflicting conceptualisations of Europeanisation within an external migration agenda.

Thereby, we will build on assumptions of post-functionalist integration theory, which underscores the importance of politicization of "Europe" by Member State governments. This report aims to show that the European Commission operates in a discursive space that is deeply structured by domestic politics.

Our report starts by providing brief background knowledge on milestones of European integration in the realm of immigration and asylum. The subsequent section proposes a conceptual framework to the study of Europeanisation and European integration that focuses on domestic aspects of political construction of substantive policy issues as well as claims of

political authority over the Europeanisation narrative. Section 4 offers insights into our empirical findings within the seven Member States and section 5 discusses findings with regard to the EU Commission.

2. Background: European integration in the area of immigration and asylum in the EU

The European integration process has never been smooth in the area of immigration and asylum. Two dimensions of conflict have determined the development of these policy fields. On the one hand, there is a tension between harmonization on the basis of supranational governance and the sovereignty-preserving coordination of national systems. On the other hand, we find a conflict between the state-centred primacy of internal security (i.e. national border control) and how that could affect universal human rights. Furthermore, demographically ageing societies and low-skilled labour shortages introduce an economic dimension to the debate, which cuts across the management of asylum based on reception and protection policies.

In line with neo-functionalist integration theory, one might argue that the creation of a Single Market and the establishment of the Schengen Area after the early 1990s would have led to a spill-over, ensuring that member states foster cooperation on the management of external migration and asylum (Bendel & Servent, 2017). However, in spite of a joint understanding that the abolishment of intra-Schengen borders created a lack of control on the movements and activities of third country nationals, the question of how related cooperation and policies would look like was far from resolved. Ever since the Dublin Convention, signed in 1990, a gap remained between European claims to fairness and solidarity found in the early policy documents (Thielemann, 2003), and the harsh reality with member states trying to preserve national sovereignty.

Even following the creation of the Area of Freedom, Justice and Security under the Amsterdam Treaty, national governments sought to keep decision-making intergovernmental, relying on unanimity and sticking to consultation procedures with the European Parliament. Despite the imbalances inscribed in the Dublin System, first generation EU directives were passed, establishing minimum standards and rights for third country nationals who settled down in a Member States, along with harmonized rules for family reunification and asylum procedures.

The Lisbon Treaty strengthened Europe's supranational institutions – the Commission, the Parliament, and the European Court of Justice – and led to co-decision-making. In the past decade, the EU witnessed a thematic expansion of its agenda, which included a stronger harmonization of asylum systems, first steps towards common labour migrant admission policies and a comprehensive foreign policy agenda in which migration policy goals are linked to development policy priorities. However, the sudden increase in the number of irregular external migrant arrivals in 2015 exerted a considerable impact on the management of external migration both at the EU and member state levels. In the context of the so-called refugee crisis and in view of highly emotive domestic discourses, the EU retreated to ad-hoc action and witnessed an increasing reliance on the EU Council to overcome conflicts over its migration agenda (Roos, 2017). This context also provided ample space for discursive governance

(Korkut et. al. 2015) of external migration including border management, protection and reception related policies.

3. Conceptual approach: politicizing EU policies and political authority at the national level

Given the fact that asylum and immigration are no longer subject to intergovernmental policy making but actually take place in a political system *sui generis*, it does not come as a surprise that in recent years the study of European integration and Europeanization has turned away from studying *why* to investigating *how* cooperation takes place and policy regimes have been harmonized.

Our approach starts from the assumption that European integration, as the transfer of originally national policy areas to the EU, and Europeanization, as the responsive process to EU norms in Member States, are two deeply interrelated phenomena (Ladrech, 2014). Specifically, we adopt a post-functionalist perspective (Hooghe & Marks, 2009) which emphasises national politicization of EU norms, procedures and actors. Thus, while there might be external pressure to delegate authority to supranational institutions – for example due to a sudden increase of external immigration – domestic political discourse can shape the way in which existing EU norms are perceived and which integration trajectories become more or less acceptable in the future. By politicizing specific issues such as the adoption of refugees, domestic politicians inevitably also connect their claims to more or less explicit views of political authority and where it should be located. On the one hand, the call for refugee distribution quotas is itself an implicit expression of support for supranational institutions. Border protection narratives, on the other hand, are often tied to an explicit expression of the failure of the EU to protect its external borders, thus prompting member states to reclaim some of their pre-Schengen authority over national borders.

A useful heuristic to distinguish positions of political groups and parties vis-à-vis the EU is the typology by Kopecký and Mudde (2002). They argue that the position of political parties runs across two dimensions, one relating to support for European integration, namely a sharing of political authority, the other relating to support for the majority of policy ideas that are institutionalized within the EU. In this vein they distinguish between four groups. First, there are Eurosceptics, who “support the general ideas of European integration, but are pessimistic about the EU’s current and/or future reflection of these ideas” (Kopecký & Mudde, 2002). Second, there are Europragmatists, who “do not support the general ideas of European integration underlying the EU, nor do they necessarily oppose them, yet they do support the EU (Kopecký & Mudde, 2002, p.303). Third, there are the Euroenthusiasts who “support the general ideas of European integration and believe that the EU is or will soon become the institutionalization of these ideas.” (Kopecký & Mudde, 2002 p.302). And fourth, there are the Eurorejects who “subscribe neither to the ideas underlying the process of European integration nor to the EU” (Kopecký & Mudde, 2002 p.302).

It is important to consider these dynamics against the background of informal EU policy-making rules, which are driven by consensus. Although most decisions in the realm of Justice and Home affairs do not require unanimity in the Council, the legislative bodies of the EU typically seek to reach broad consensus, even to the point of including extreme dissident voices. The

European Commission, which has a monopoly on legislative proposals, frames political problem definitions in a crucial way and thereby has to bridge an increasingly broad spectrum of member state positions. As we will discuss further below, it has also not shied away from incorporating claims and narratives of far-right anti-immigration governments in recent years.

4. Empirical findings I: political claims and narratives on migration and the EU in 7 Member States

In this section, we take a closer look at how governmental actors in different EU Member States politicized European immigration and asylum policies as well as the EU itself as container of political authority. We group the seven countries of our study into three clusters: the central and northern group composed of Germany, Austria, and Sweden; the eastern group composed of Hungary and Poland; and the southern group composed of Greece and Italy.

The northern and central group: Germany, Austria, and Sweden

During the peak of the migration crisis of 2015, the central and northern European countries Austria, Germany and Sweden constituted the three main destinations for newly arriving refugees. Relative to the size of population, each of them adopted a considerable number of applicants into their asylum systems; at the same time, each of them also introduced a series of similar restrictive measures starting from late 2015/early 2016. These included, for example, the repeated and prolonged intra-Schengen border controls and time limitations to protection statuses as well as restrictions of associated rights. Germany and Austria had centrist grand coalition governments, while in Sweden, the Social Democrats and the Greens relied on legislative support from the conservative and liberal block.

Despite their similar settings, we came across finely nuanced but surprisingly diverse political narratives among political leaders in these three states. An undisputed assumption, shared across a wide spectrum, was that the European Union represents the institutional vehicle to solve related issues, notwithstanding that for some political actors it was to blame for existing failures of migration management. The question then focuses on what role political elites envisioned for European coordination and where they placed member states within this coordination. As it shall become apparent below, policy rationales in the field of migration and asylum are inherently linked to the political leaders' particular conceptions of power division within the Union.

Debates on border control are a good example. While all the three countries had similar approaches to the reintroduction of intra-Schengen border controls, the Austrian government promoted a very distinct narrative. Most notably, the conservative coalition partner, the ÖVP, sought to legitimise border controls by pointing to the principle of subsidiarity. The argument presented was that the EU failed to protect its external borders and that some member states enabled "unrestricted admission". While its socialist coalition partner aligned with the German chancellor, the conservatives frequently sought to juxtapose their position to what was constructed as an "open border policy" in Germany. The German government, although effectively pursuing a similar border policy like Austria, adopted a narrative of taking responsibility. It thus also took a lot of heat at home, with some CSU members making common cause with the far-right AfD, which at that time had not entered the federal parliament.

However, interestingly, the German government was the driving force behind the European externalization strategy via the EU-Turkey deal.

Similar to the German government, the Swedish social democrats, Greens and the conservative Moderates displayed unity by adopting a liberal stance and arguing in favour of European solidarity driven by supranational institutions rather than national isolation. The so-called Swedish “U-turn” in asylum policy was adopted with a public display of discontent on the part the government and a realist argument of being overburdened. Burden-sharing, in terms of a systematic distribution of asylum seekers across Member States, indeed appeared as a viable solution to many governmental figures in the early days of the crisis. The German chancellor, even though more pronounced about this idea in 2015 than later on, combined the call for obligatory quotas with a euro-enthusiastic claim to humanitarianism. Not least due to a comparably strong sensitivity for human rights obligations and concern for international reputation, her approach found broad support among German political elites. Furthermore, unlike in Austria, German politics displayed a strong discursive nexus between humanitarianism and the demographic and economic benefits of a comparatively young immigrant population. In Austria, this link was largely rejected – by conservatives and right-wing populists – as ground for legitimizing ethnic diversity and by social democrats as a way of increasing competition on the labour market. The Swedish government displayed the strongest account of humanitarianism by arguing that the EU simply had responsibilities towards refugees, one of which implies saving lives in the Mediterranean and accommodating those who arrive safely. Like Germany, Sweden sought to lead as an example of European humanitarianism and solidarity. Again, the major counter-discourse to a broad political elite consensus came from a rising far-right party, namely the Sweden Democrats.

Considering the political claims made by political leaders in government, Austria seems to take a particularly restrictive position within the central-northern block. Indeed, the narratives deployed by the Social Democratic chancellors during the crisis suggested a liberal Europeanisation trajectory similar to that of Germany (even though with a stronger emphasis on the problem of immigrant integration). Yet, more than in the other two countries, Austria’s coalition partners displayed early signs of deep division. The Conservatives of the ÖVP who held the posts of interior and foreign affairs ministers soon adopted restrictive narratives that had traditionally been fostered by the established far-right Freedom party (FPÖ). Thus, it came as no surprise when the ÖVP terminated the coalition in 2017 and started to collaborate with the FPÖ following the Conservatives’ considerable electoral success driven by anti-immigration slogan. Conversely, the FPÖ gave up its euro-rejectionist position and turned towards a more pragmatist position. Germany continued its grand coalition but saw the rise of the far-right AfD, which entered the *Bundestag* in 2017 as the strongest opposition party. Likewise, in Sweden the far-right Sweden democrats established themselves in the *Riksdag* and represent the second strongest opposition party today.

The northern block demonstrates how precisely those far-right parties might be a decisive explanatory factor for diverging narratives on the future course of European cooperation and integration. They do not necessarily propose positions and claims with regard to a rejection or embrace of the European Union and integration per se, but they can exert pressure on centrist parties and discursively shape principles, values and modes of governance that inform European policy-making. Considering the fact that the idea of obligatory distribution quotas for asylum seekers has come off the table in EU negotiations and the securitization of external border control turned into the primary goal in asylum politics, it seems as though far-right discourses have been able to make a crucial difference.

4.1. The eastern group: Hungary and Poland

The issue of political authority in Europe was most fiercely politicised in the eastern group. Right-wing political parties in government and emblematic political figures such as the Hungarian Prime Minister Viktor Orbán emerged as the most vocal anti-immigrant voices in Europe. What is also noteworthy is that the political opposition in Poland and Hungary is comparatively silent and partly complicit with the security-oriented migration politics of the conservative right. In other words, unlike the northern/central and the southern group, we can say that migration politics did not see much contention across the political spectrum. Even in Poland, initial divergences between the conservative Law and Justice Party (PiS) and the liberal right Civic Platform (PO) disappeared over time. While in 2015, the PO government supported the EU decision on compulsory quotas for the relocation of refugees from hotspots, later influenced by public opinion and as a result of lost elections, the PO tightened the party position on this matter, recognizing that the dispersal of refugees must be voluntary and the emphasis in EU policy should be on the control of the EU's external borders. At the same time, the Civic Platform made it clear that it was not going to endorse "illegal migrants" should it take power. In this way, the position of this party towards migration has clearly come close to the policy of the ruling PiS (Grosse 2018).

In Hungary, the lack of discursive diversity in migration politics even turned into a one-man show of Viktor Orbán, who had turned into an anti-immigrant voice at a European scale and received much praise from right-wing politicians, including the extreme right, in other EU states.

Yet, insofar as the migration politics of incumbent governments did not face much contention from the opposition, their position on the future of EU integration and external migration in time solidified. Equally, the Hungarian and Polish political parties showed that by opposing an increased role for the EU reception and protection of migrants, and in particular their dispersal through the quota regime, they could present themselves as the true Europeans that were telling the truth about the danger that migrants posed for the future of Europe. For this reason, we associate the Hungarian and Polish conservative right with a euro-pragmatic attitude rather than a euro-rejectionist even if they were opposing a very important instrument of European integration of migration policy, i.e., the quota regime.

There were a few noteworthy reflections in the discourses of politicians in Hungary and Poland in view of Europe and migration. Both Fidesz in Hungary and PiS (partly also PO) in Poland considered their countries as EU frontier states. This is noteworthy as until the last decade or even 2015, the southern states, mainly Greece and Italy, would have been conceived as the EU border states. The enlargement and the sudden increase in the number of external migrant arrivals in 2015 made Hungary appear as a major frontier state. Notwithstanding the political importance that the eastern border has for the EU, Poland cannot be argued as strongly affected by irregular arrivals throughout the 2015 crisis. In both countries, there was an attempt to shift the blame to Germany, as well as what is referred to as the liberal EU establishment, represented by the European Commission, as per Orbán's discourse, for letting migrants into Europe with false promises of integration. One crucial aspect of their narrative lies in their particular conception of solidarity, which is coined as solidarity for Europe rather than for the European Union. Both Hungarian and Polish politicians declared that in fact their primary objective was to be in solidarity with their own publics. Orbán went even further to claim that in fact the security-oriented migration politics that his government pursued made him a true European. Therefore, neither the Polish nor the Hungarian governments conceived that opposing EU-led admission policies would imply a Euro-rejectionists position. Instead, their argument was that they were serving Europe better by rejecting any migration policy introduced

at the EU-level and by promoting what they conceived as European public interest with their security focused migration policies. We take this as a further sign of how euro-pragmatism evolved as a position inasmuch as the political parties in the eastern group mitigated their migration politics to project what they set as priorities for their domestic politics as plans for the future shape of Europeanization.

4.2. The southern group: Greece and Italy

Southern Europe endured the worst of the Eurozone crisis after 2008, and a mixture of geography and the Dublin Regulations meant the region was equally central to the politicisation of asylum. The outcome has been a decade of turbulence, dominated by EU demands for austerity and a Europe-wide dissensus over reallocation mechanisms. Southern European attitudes to the EU are thus among the continent's most hostile. This has led, in the two countries considered here, to swings from anti-establishment to emergency technocratic rule. Indeed, the Greek Prime Minister Lucas Papademos and Italy's Mario Monti, both politically independent former bankers and academic economists, were appointed within days of one another. Equally, both countries have been ruled by governments actively committed to conflict with European institutions, ranging from Greece's Syriza to Italy's Silvio Berlusconi, Lega Nord (LN) and the Five Star Movement (M5S). Given the above, it follows that, in assessing Southern European narratives against the European Union, it is difficult to disentangle grievances against imposed economic hardships from xenophobic attitudes towards migrants. Thus, it is crucial to note how political issues were constructed and by whom.

Where left-wing parties have held power, as with Greece's Syriza, they have sought to combine opposition to xenophobia and "fortress Europe" with calls for EU-wide solutions to relieve the burden on border states. The Syriza Prime Minister Alexis Tsipras put it as follows, "I am of the opinion that the protection of the EU borders and the external dimension of the migration crisis must be taken equally seriously. The EU should focus on sharing responsibility and not the burden of falling on the host countries". While asserting that refugee management was a clear left-versus-right ideological issue, solutions turned on reallocation of refugees to other, less affected areas of the continent. The EU's failure to impose such mechanisms was a persistent source of conflict. Thus, a rhetoric of European solidarity was often framed against the actually existing EU structures. Syriza asserted that "the refugee issue is a common European issue" but equally "the drama of millions of refugees reveals the blatant failure of a sovereign European policy, both in addressing the migratory-refugee phenomenon, and with regard to the Common Foreign and Security Policy of the EU". As it becomes evident, alternative visions for European integration have not necessarily been confined to the continent's populist right. While Syriza explicitly adopted a populist framing of politics that conflict with a European establishment, their politics did not conform to the anti-pluralism often associated with populist rhetoric. Indeed, their criticisms centred on the EU's failure to achieve pluralism and humanitarianism in practice.

Italy's successive crises have taken a different dynamic that largely pitches an anti-establishment right against a technocratic, Europhile centre-left. M5S has played an intermediary role, entering coalition with the right-populist LN then latterly with the technocratic-left Democratic Party (PD), under the leadership of the non-affiliated Giuseppe Conte, in the so-called "technopopulist" alliance. This confusion reflects M5S's eclectic ideological origins, which combines left-populist economics with more right-wing stances on immigration, and party structures which allow significant sway to online plebiscites. Effectively, M5S has been incorporated to combat the charismatic power of LN leader Matteo Salvini, who has succeeded Silvio Berlusconi as the dominant presence in Italian politics.

Salvini has weaponised grievances around migration to help LN move beyond its traditional Northern bases and become a dominating force in Italian politics. His rhetoric accentuates fears of “terrorists and criminals hidden in barges” and similar rhetorical tropes. Equally, Salvini has pursued a vigorous critique of EU leaders (“governed by dangerous hypocrites”) combined with an ambivalence about EU membership. At times, Salvini straightforwardly adopted a euro-rejectionist stance and called for an abandonment of the Eurozone and the EU, in favour of a return to Italian sovereignty. However, proximity to power served to weaken these combative stances. Having run on the slogan “No Euro” in 2014, by 2019 Salvini was calling the Eurozone “irreversible”: “The [Northern] League is not thinking about Italy’s exit from the euro or the European Union”. Salvini has thus been central to putative pan-European alliances for a sovereigntist “Europe of the nations”. Conversely, Salvini’s critics have appealed to European institutions to relieve Italy’s burdens, but often with little success. The EU’s failure to negotiate collective solutions to successive crises – now including, as of 2020, the coronavirus pandemic – put the Italian forces ranged against Salvini in difficult positions.

The Southern European cases also highlight the unevenness of European experiences. Historically, these cases have been influenced by legacies of authoritarianism and weak state authority; geographically, by their proximity to the Mediterranean; economically, by an earlier history of socioeconomic imbalances. Their EU membership initially appeared to offer both economic and political development benefits. Latterly, it has also imposed significant (and, many would concede, unfair) burdens on Southern European states, and relations have become dysfunctional. Governments of all political stripes have been forced to reckon with the attendant problems. While Syriza pursued a relatively lax border regime, the intensity of austerity measures imposed on the country meant that conditions for migrants became a byword for inhumane squalor. The contradictions of the European humanitarian ideology thus became concentrated on very particular geographical zones.

A common theme across all Southern European politics has been a critique of the Dublin Regulation. This has effectively worked to concentrate the “burdens” of asylum in particular geographies, and themes of burden appear in the rhetoric of all governing parties, regardless of ideology. Under these circumstances, and given ongoing demands for austerity, conflict with EU institutions has formed an inescapable fact of government.

In the following section, we will turn our discussion to the new EU Commission and question which political assumptions and narratives that we found across the three country clusters were echoed in its most recent policy proposals over its most recent policy agenda.

5. Empirical findings II: the EU Commission echoing national claims and narratives

Two recent documents set the stage for the migration policy paradigm of the new Commission, namely the “EU Migration and Asylum Package” introduced in September 2020 and the “European Way of Life” agenda that was established in 2019. The incoming executive of the European Commission nominated a vice-president for migration and security issues bearing the title of “Commissioner for *protecting* the European way of life”. This allusion to a continent under threat and in need of protection prompted months of controversy about the meaning attached to European borders and boundaries. The centre-right European People’s Party,

which proposed the title, insisted they had not meant to raise the drawbridge against refugees: "this means to rescue people in the Mediterranean...not to close harbours". Nonetheless, both supporters and critics interpreted it as a move to absorb populist right narratives. Marine le Pen hailed "an ideological victory"; by contrast, socialist and green MEPs saw it as surrender to a notion of an embattled "European civilisation" promoted in the rhetoric of leaders like Hungary's Viktor Orbán. The controversy would eventually force a small but crucial change, with *protecting* becoming *promoting* the European way of life. But the polarised reaction had already established a crucial fact about the continent's political identity. Henceforth, it is nearly impossible to speak of the "European way of life" without insinuating fear of foreign intruders.

5.1. The "European way of life" agenda from 2019

The agenda calls for further cooperation and solidarity among EU member states for handling migration and appeals to the securitization of migration politics of right-wing European governments. As we discussed above, narrativizing migration through a security lens has been a dominant element across all countries under study. As the focus on migration management remains security focused, we can also see how border protection and securitised discourses have entered this document. In this vein, the European Commission (2020, p.3) introduced its aim to modernize the management of the its external borders through new and upgraded large-scale information systems, with reinforced support by Frontex and eu-LISA, and to ensure systematic checks at the EU's external borders. This effort responds to the demands of some member states such as Poland and Hungary to re-interpret the EU's role in migration management and to make a shift from facilitating refugee admission (i.e. the quota regime) to providing border security.

A prominent expression of the security-based discourse of migration in the European way of life agenda has been an apparent inclination to categorize migrants as "legal" or "illegal". The terminology of illegality and irregularity places a particularly strong stigma of doubt on asylum seekers who are usually forced to embark on an irregular journey. At the same time, Margaritis Schinas, the Vice-President for the "European Way of Life" agenda (2019, p.8) reiterated that being European means being open to the world and helping those who were less fortunate. However, this humanitarian focus has at the same time appears to suggest economic returns for the EU. As Ylva Johansson, the Commissioner for Home Affairs stated that "[w]e face an increasing need for legal migration for our labour markets to remain competitive, to face the long-term demographic challenges" (2019, p.10). This suggests that legality and humanitarianism have become ever bound up with the benefits that some migrants are to offer to the EU and its economic competitiveness. While this goes against the discourses of Hungarian and Polish politicians, who questioned integration and argued that it was impossible, it is still aligned with migration politics in Germany. Yet, the EU officials also used "illegal" as a qualifier for those migrants that posed a security threat for the "European Way of Life". Clearly reflecting Viktor Orbán's discourse that migrant smugglers are the reason of illegal immigration, this suggests that the new Commission seeks to appeal to a feeling of insecurity already attached to external migration.

5.2. The EU Migration and Asylum Package from 2020

The "EU Migration and Asylum Package" that was introduced in September 2020 is a worrying attempt to embed feelings of insecurity into policy. The narratives surrounding this proposal refer to border security, humanitarianism, sovereignty, externalisation, talent and labour migration and finally efficient and coordinated returns. In this order, the EU seeks to establish a coordinated border security system to protect the Mediterranean border. It delegates

humanitarianism to “efficient” asylum decisions at the border. To serve the priorities of those that particularly demanded more externalisation and supported a hotspot approach, in this respect, the document praises externalisation agreements thus far and recommends developing them further. Meanwhile, by speaking of the need for “legal” migrants, the pact also reiterates the need for talent and labour migration. However, the implication of this is that the EC effectively excluded unregulated migration from its scope of legality.

The difficulties arising from the Commission’s effort to create consensus among Member States are clearest on issues of responsibility and burden sharing. The mandatory admission quota, which emerged from centrist and left-wing parties in 2015, disappeared from the political agenda, most likely due to the resistance of countries like Hungary, the Czech Republic and Austria. As the political discourse had shifted rightwards, the Commission confined its ambitions of solidarity to the concept of flexible solidarity. Therefore, it proposed a financial incentive system for the admission of refugee during normal times. During periods of crisis, a mechanism for mandatory solidarity would kick in, obliging to member states to take in refugees or to express their solidarity by supporting other states with deportation procedures.

These two documents appear to show an attempt to reach out to populist politicians, to append their agendas to the future course of Europeanisation in migration governance at the supranational level. Humanitarian obligations are contextualized within a crisis management framework, whereas asylum applications are referred to status determination at the border in an “efficient” way. This is perhaps the most acute resonance of the Hungarian narrative onto the new migration pact. These decisions at the border are to accompany pre-screening, i.e. health, identification and security checks, assuming that all migrants would have appropriate documentation in place. As a further element of externalization, finally, the Pact asks for harmonization of rules with third countries. This ambiguous and ambitious agenda raises questions on externalization and how it is prone to become a tit-for-tat sovereignty issue between the transit states and the EU – all leaving the welfare and rights of migrants in peril.

6. Conclusion

In this comparative report, we sought to describe some key political claims and narratives on migration and the EU across three country clusters and to provide a deeper understanding of how certain ideas from the national level are mirrored in the EU Commission’s policy proposals. As became evident, the crisis of migration governance was a critical juncture for party politics across Europe and demonstrated once more the deficiencies of the Common European Asylum System. In particular, the question of responsibility and burden sharing called for joint action and solidarity among member states. However, the meaning of solidarity was deeply contested across European governments and political parties. The introduction of an ad hoc relocation quota in 2015 and the widespread resistance to its implementation marked the beginning of the end for the distribution paradigm. By contrast, we witnessed how solidarity was interpreted in terms of a protection of borders, whereby the restoration of a country’s national sovereignty was argued to also protect other Member States. In this vein, the spirit of the Dublin Convention prevails and political authority was increasingly reclaimed for the nation-state. Securitization discourses that primarily circulate around conceptions of border control were first driven by far-right parties as well as conservative parties in Eastern Europe. Later they entered mainstream parties and established a hegemony that is mirrored in the flexible

solidarity concept by the European Commission. It remains to be seen how its legislative proposal from 2020 will develop and, particularly, whether the European Parliament will come up with alternative conceptions of solidarity for the future of the European Union.

Ultimately, the question remains where the EU migration governance can be contextualized at the nexus of supranationalism and inter-governmentalism, and how this affects *conflicting conceptualisations* of Europeanisation among the EU member states as per migration politics and policies. The WP6 reports and this comparative report sought to raise a question, to this extent, about the relevance of established conceptualisations of what makes Euro-reject, Euro-sceptic, and Euro-enthusiast political positions. The finding is that a self-perception of a political party on a rejection to enthusiasm spectrum of Europeanisation is not the same as how they are perceived by the European supranational institutions. In order to understand this disparity, we need to study and understand how political leaders narrativized their politics in an effort to bolster domestic audiences. This has become particularly acute in Hungarian politics. While the European supranational institutions consistently depicted Fidesz-led Hungary as a Euro-sceptic or Euro-reject party, Orbán himself proposed that Hungary was in fact acting on behalf of Europe to defend it from intruders. The Polish case also resembles Hungary. However, the crucial variable in these two countries was how the opposition could not produce any alternative discourse concerning refugee admission policies.

Beyond the eastern group, we stress the historical Euroscepticism in the southern group, which was conditioned by the Troika's austerity politics during the economic crisis. However, when it came to narratives of border security, politicians in both Greece and Italy sought to present their countries as defenders of European borders. Hence, their Euroscepticism dissipated when they faced the imagined threat posed by the "other" personified by the external migrant. It is noteworthy that the extent to which a country follows Europeanisation is affected by which audience their political parties are presenting their European identity. By drawing a line between "us" the "them", they would appear European, but facing the self they would have more space to qualify the way they coopt Europeanisation. Finally, an attempt to upload domestic policy preferences to the European level has appeared most distinctly in the Central and Northern group, where Europe emerged as a solution to the problem that external migration posed to national politics. However, we should also note that this group of states attempted to attach their policy preferences to the European level after having realized that domestic solutions were failing. In this case, one can say that their relative Euro-enthusiasm was affected by their national political preferences. This shows that even Euro-enthusiasm – an apparently most supranational policy stance on Europeanisation – is prone to be affected by domestic political preferences. Considering this context, WP6 proposes that Europeanisation theories require the consideration of ever more complex and identity-focused narratives, both European and national, in order to understand the cacophony of policies at the member state level when faced with external migration.

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